

SIGGRAPH 東京
ASIA 2024
TOKYO

Conference | 3–6 December 2024

Exhibition | 4–6 December 2024

Venue | Tokyo International Forum, Japan

Rudimentary Examples of Composing with Generative AI for Immersive Applications

CAROUSEL+ has received funding from the European Union's Future Emerging Technology Pathfinder ProAct scheme under grant agreement id: 101017779.

Edinburgh Napier
UNIVERSITY

Professor of Video Game Technology

Chief Technology Officer

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ALLIEDMAGIC+

Kenny Mitchell
farpeek.com

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koelnmesse

Real-time XR Challenge of Generative AI Methods

- Need to generate images $<0.00833\text{ms}$ ($>120\text{fps}$)

Select your timezone: (GMT+9:00) Tokyo, Seoul, Osaka, Sapporo, Yaki

MidJourney Response Server

Should I use Relax Mode right now?

Model	Current Waiting Time	Recommendation
v6	~28 seconds	Only if you're not in a rush. 🐢
v6up	~56 seconds	Yikes! Time to grab a coffee. ☕
Niji6	~7 seconds	Go for it! It ain't getting much faster. ⚡

Real-time Challenge of GenAI

- Stable Diffusion with ControlNet Benchmark
- Video Diffusion Transformers (DiT) have lower per frame cost
 - LTX Video <https://replicate.com/fofr/ltx-video> 0.05ms
- Need to be >3 orders of magnitude faster

Natural Interaction

- Live AI chat friends in Augmented Reality
- Real-time face animation from LLM tokens
- Can still misunderstand allophones in speech recognition (sail != sale...)

L. Casas, K. Mitchell '[Intermediated Reality with an AI 3D Printed Character](#)', in SIGGRAPH '23: ACM SIGGRAPH 2023 Real-Time Live!

MoodFlow

- Real-time sentiment analysis of speech
- to generate empathic full body animation responses with LLM driven speech
- So, in this way more context from emotion analysis
 - we can reduce confusion of speech recognition and build more natural whole avatar responses

I am feeling great! Excited to go to IEEE VR in Orlando!

L. Casas, S. Hannah, K. Mitchell 'MoodFlow: Orchestrating Conversations with Emotionally Intelligent Avatars in Mixed Reality', in 2024 IEEE VR Workshop on Animation in Virtual and Augmented Environments.

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HoloJig

- Instead of laboriously generating a traditional 3D scene with low quality results
 - we developed HoloJig to create generative AI scene from spoken prompts
- Recipe
 - Generate panorama images from voiced prompts
 - generate inferred depth using MiDaS/DepthAnything
 - Live render parallax mapping according to this depth

Llogari Casas, Kenny Mitchell, Monica Tamariz, Samantha Hannah, David Sinclair, Babis Koniaris, Jessie Kennedy 'Design Considerations of Voice Articulated Generative AI Virtual Reality Dance Environments', in 2024 ACM CHI Workshop on [Generative AI in User Generated Content](#),

Speech
Driven
GenAI

HoloJig

- Speech driven world transformation latency
- Experimenting with blending between gen AI worlds

HoloJig: Instant Online Virtual Dance Spaces with Generative AI Vocal Descriptions

Llogari Casas, Kenny Mitchell, Monica Tamariz, Samantha Hannah, David Sinclair, Babis Koniaris, Jessie Kennedy 'Design Considerations of Voice Articulated Generative AI Virtual Reality Dance Environments', in 2024 ACM CHI Workshop on [Generative AI in User Generated Content](#),

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Voice Controlled GenAI Avatars

- ControlNet with structured prompt guidance
- Large screen with camera showing AR view of class with stylization of dance styles, etc.
- Role embodiment providing potential of enhanced training, e.g. for dance poses

Llogari Casas, Kenny Mitchell 'Structured Teaching Prompt Articulation for Generative-AI Role Embodiment with Augmented Mirror Video Displays', in *The 19th ACM SIGGRAPH International Conference on the Virtual-Reality Continuum and its Applications in Industry, VRCAI 2024*

GenAI with an Audience

- GenAI for large audience XR stylization
 - ControlNet with inferred depth
- Recipe to animate in real-time
 - Generate keyframes and interpolate
 - using optical flow
 - and prediction [Synchronized patterned motion avatars](#) patent

worldlabs.ai this week

GenAI for Free Roaming Worlds

- With depth panoramas we have some limited movement in VR, as we've seen in WorldLabs.ai web demos this week
 - But how to free-roam in a landscape?
 - What's an efficient scheme for lightfield videos?
- Two works
 - IRIDIUM streamed compressed full motion light fields
 - VoxSpars an optimized primitive for point cloud rendering

C. Koniaris, M. Kosek, D. Sinclair, and K. Mitchell '[Compressed Animated Light Fields with Real-Time View-Dependent Reconstruction](#)', *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 1666–1680, 2019

E. Waite, A. Murray, C. Ross, J. Jamroz, S. Mitchell, A. Bradley, K. Mitchell '[Generating Real-time Detailed Ground Visualisations from Sparse Aerial Point Clouds](#)', in *2022 ACM SIGGRAPH European Conference on Visual Media Production*

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Questions?